

DANCE TOURISM: DANCING AS A KIND OF ART

¹Iroda Yakupbayeva, ²Nargiza Akhrorova, ³Jasorat Sharipova

¹Student at "Silk Road" International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

²Lecturer at "Silk Road" International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

³Teacher at Samarkand state school number 67

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Abstract. *This article aims to explore the concept of dance as an artistic medium and examines how it affects society, self-expression, and travel. It discusses the expressive and emotional possibilities of dance, showcasing it as a universal language that transcends spoken language. It draws attention to dance's significance in the development of human culture and its ability to convey ideas, feelings, and narratives. It also explores the idea of dance tourism, a cutting-edge and quickly expanding trend in the contemporary travel industry. For dance fans, this means taking part in a variety of dancing events at the trip's destination, which makes it an amazing and exhilarating experience. The commentary also emphasizes how important dance is for fostering intercultural dialogue and understanding since it facilitates interpersonal interaction.*

Key words: dancing, art, dance tourism, dance and culture, body language, movements.

Аннотация. *Этот аннотация нацелена на изучение концепции танца как художественного средства и рассматривает, как он влияет на общество, самовыражение и путешествия. Рассматриваются выразительные и эмоциональные возможности танца, показывающие его как универсальный язык, превосходящий разговорную речь. Привлекается внимание к значению танца в развитии человеческой культуры и его способности передавать идеи, чувства и повествования. В ней также рассматривается идея танцевального туризма - передового и быстро развивающегося направления в современной индустрии путешествий. Для поклонников танца это означает участие в разнообразных танцевальных мероприятиях в месте назначения путешествия, что делает его удивительным и захватывающим опытом. В комментарии также подчеркивается, насколько важен танец для развития межкультурного диалога и взаимопонимания, поскольку он способствует межличностному взаимодействию.*

Ключевые слова: танец, искусство, танцевальный туризм, танец и культура, язык тела, движения.

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola raqs tushunchasini badiiy vosita sifatida o'rganishga qaratilgan va uning jamiyatga, o'zini namoyon qilishga va sayohatga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganadi. U raqsning ekspressiv va hissiy imkoniyatlarini muhokama qiladi, uni og'zaki tildan ustun turadigan universal til sifatida namoyish etadi. U raqsning insoniyat madaniyati rivojidadagi ahamiyatiga, uning g'oyalar, his-tuyg'ular va hikoyalarni etkazish qobiliyatiga e'tibor qaratadi. Shuningdek, u raqs turizmi g'oyasini o'rganadi, bu zamonaviy sayyohlik industriyasining eng ilg'or va tez rivojlanayotgan tendentsiyasi. Raqs ishqibozlari uchun bu sayohat manzilida turli raqs tadbirlarida qatnashishni anglatadi, bu esa uni hayratlanarli va hayajonli tajribaga aylantiradi. Sharh, shuningdek, raqs madaniyatlararo muloqot va tushunishni rivojlantirish uchun qanchalik muhimligini ta'kidlaydi, chunki u shaxslararo o'zaro ta'sirni osonlashtiradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: raqs, san'at, raqs turizmi, raqs va madaniyat, tana tili, harakatlar.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays dancing is one of the integral parts of our lives. The art of dancing appeared in ancient times. The ancient Greeks were distinguished by a special love for this art, and treated dancing as a gift from the Gods. Overall dance considers as a way to express the mood and feelings with the help of body movements. This article explores the meaning and way of dance's representation, how it effects to culture, dance tourism, and how this type of tourism effects on the country. Dance does not consist of only particular meaningless movements; it has deeper meaning. Additionally, dance requires not only the participation of the body, but also the soul and mind. When it comes to trips made solely for the purpose of participating in or witnessing dance-related activities are called dance tourism. This may include attending dance events, learning to dance, conducting workshops, or just watching a show. Thanks to the universal language of dance, dance tourism allows people to fully immerse themselves in the art and culture of a particular place. For those who show great interest in dancing, it can be a great pastime.

Dancing is a Universal Language for Communicating Inner Serenity and Emotions.

People who dance are not allowed to speak or represent their feelings with the help of words. "A dancer's instrument is her body" (Graham, 2015, as cited in Carter, 2015). It means that they use particular movements in order to show emotions. Many emotions including love, joy, grief, rage, confidence, and many more, were conveyed through each pose, jump, and movement. Expressing feelings that are frequently difficult to put into words, including wrath, fear, disappointment, or loss, is much easier when done through spontaneous movements. Dreams, fantasies, hopes, and disappointments can all be expressed through dance. Dancing, everyone feels something different, most often it's delight, elation, but sometimes it's negative emotions...anger, resentment, hatred. With the help of dance, people can turn their destructive feelings into those that will revive them, heal them. Arnheim (2015, as cited in Johnson, 2010) said that "when we watch a dancer, the sadness or happiness of the mood seems to be directly inherent in the movements themselves". "Unlike all other art forms ... dance is literally embodied in the moving human form" (Stevens, 2005). The human self is best expressed with the help of movement, and by fostering physical flexibility, we foster spiritual flexibility. Natural gestures are a good way to represent feelings, and sign language can reveal things about a person that they are unable or unwilling to say. "Our capacity to create and appreciate dance and music is based in our drive to reach out to others in contingent interaction through time; we wish to participate in the gestures of co-ordinated companionship" (Malloch, 2005). It is true that a strong sense of interpersonal connection based on shared experiences and interactions is necessary both to create dance and music and to enjoy them. Both music and dance are able to awaken the feelings of the audience, convey cultural concepts and unite people in joint artistic expression. Thanks to this shared experience, people can always connect and communicate in a way that overcomes language barriers, which leads to the creation of a unique form of self-expression that can make a huge difference for both artists and viewers. It is true that a strong sense of interpersonal connection based on shared experiences and interactions is necessary both to create dance and music and to enjoy them. Both music and dance are able to awaken the feelings of the audience, convey cultural concepts and unite people in joint artistic expression. Thanks to this shared experience, people can always connect and communicate in a way that overcomes language barriers, which leads to the creation of a unique form of self-expression that can make a huge difference for both artists and viewers.. There is an unearthly power in dance. This power affects to the inner state and awakens a variety of feelings. An example is the words of O'connor, who stated: "I tried to get a sense of how dancers felt during the performance' and found that performing helped to give them a very

positive sense of self. They have all been dancing from a very early age (3-4 years in most cases) and are all highly skilled. This means that they do not have to concentrate on the steps but even if they do make a mistake it will go unnoticed by the audience. In addition, part of the pleasure of performing is the knowledge that they have a skill which is relatively rare and which cannot be easily acquired” (2003). The next paragraph will discuss how dance is deeply intertwined with culture and traditions.

Dance, like Music, Plays a very Important Role in the Development of Human Culture.

People have enjoyed dancing since ancient times, and modern dance has been used for entertainment, communication, self-expression, and the overall growth of a person's cultural identity. Naone mentioned that “dance provides a chance to study, all in once, rhythm, how the body moves through space, the coordination of the body as a whole, and its ability to synchronize to external stimuli such as music” (2007). As Gough claimed, “appreciation involves the subjective (emotions, sensations, feelings, memories) and the objective (concepts, language, form, structure) and a synthesis of both can help to find meanings.” (2015). The type of dance performed by the two partners is especially important. It varies greatly depending on the tempo of the music, such as slow and fast, classical and modern. It is known that primitive man told in dance how he hunted, fished, cultivated the land, fought his enemies, rejoiced in his successes, and experienced his sorrows. Folk dance, as a melodic and rhythmic expression of the human body, reveals human nature, thoughts and feelings about the world. Each country has its own dance language that reflects its natural, psychological and social identity. Today, dance has become an integral part of cultural dialogue between different ethnic groups and countries. Soili Hamalainen describes dance as experiential and "never the same as it is moved, as it is visual" (2009). Dancers showcase their unique styles and traditions at numerous festivals and competitions that attract dancers from all over the world. Such events help explore other cultures, exchange experiences and create new art forms. Dance also helps to broaden the audience's horizons, providing an opportunity to learn about other ethnicities and cultures. Dancers can convey emotions, stories, and ideas through body movements and facial expressions. These gestures will help you be appreciated and understood by people from other cultures and help you get used to the new culture. MacCanncll (1989), has claimed that “authenticity is the corner- stone for understanding contemporary tourism since the primary motivation for tourism in western societies is precisely a search for the authentic in an increasingly inauthentic world” (people want to see the history). In a world where people have become accustomed to striving for improvement with the help of technology, there are many people who are more interested in the origin and history of certain things. Tourists are actually looking for authenticity, but they are tricked into immersing themselves in a simulated environment and fake landscapes that are created by a tourist machine in order to take advantage of the naivety of visitors. In most cases, tourists are content with far-fetched, fake places and objects because they cannot see through the facade. And dancing is one of the few performances that were conceived not for the purpose of making visitors believe in something, but on the contrary, allow them to immerse themselves in history. This happens when presenting types of dances, such as ballet, or folk dances, which are able to convey a certain course of events in the past. This is one of the reasons for the emergence of dance tourism, which will be discussed in the next paragraph.

Discussions: Among many new concepts and ideas, a new concept has recently been developed as dance tourism.

According to Banio and Malchrowicz-Mosko, “dance tourism is understood as travel for the purpose of learning dance as a cultural phenomenon in places where those dance styles were born, or where they play an important national role as well as enjoying great popularity among the local community” (2019). Dance tourism is an exceptional direction in the modern tourism industry. This is a special form of tourism that requires you to participate in various dance events at your destination. If a person who wants to travel cannot imagine life without dance, he chooses a country or resort where music festivals or other events are planned at the time. The following are the analysis and types of dance tourism.

- Tourist and spectator: Aim is to buy tickets and travel to another country to watch professional performances.

- Tourist participants: This includes competitions for different types of tours and guest her performances, as well as participation in international festivals and dance events on your own.

-Student Tourist: The goal is to learn a particular dance style.

In general, dance tourism not only improves people's physical condition and promotes the release of endorphins that improve mood and lower stress levels, but also when people want to immerse themselves in culture and tradition. Let us help you expand your horizons and leave an unforgettable impress Below are some of the benefits of dance tourism:

1. Cultural immersion: Thanks to the distinctive dances and customs of the region, dance tourism allows visitors to immerse themselves in the local lifestyle. It provides an opportunity to get to know local communities and learn more about their traditions and lifestyle.

2. Physical and Mental Well-being: Dancing can be an excellent strategy for staying active and fit while traveling. Dancing is also associated with improving mood and reducing stress in terms of mental health.

3. Skill Development: Travelers can develop their dancing skills and learn new techniques from local teachers by participating in dance workshops. .It can also be a pleasant way to broaden your horizons and try something new.

However, there are several possible disadvantages that should be considered when traveling for dancing:

1. Cost: Attending dance festivals, classes and performances can be expensive, especially if you are going to visit famous dance venues or high-level events. The cost of food, accommodation and transportation during the trip may increase dramatically.

2. Language barriers: It may be difficult to properly interact with the local dance community or understand instructions during classes or performances if you visit a place where you do not speak the language perfectly.

3. Cultural use: It is very important that visitors participating in dance tourism are aware of the cultural roots of the dances they are getting to know and refrain from using them without the consent of the community or relevant knowledge.

Conclusions and Recommendations

When it comes to the role of tourism in the country, dance tourism plays an important role in the development of the country's tourism, attracting tourists interested in participating or watching local dance performances, festivals and other events. According to some researchers, a dance performance even for tourists, unlike many other artistic expressions, still remains the most authentic and creative act (Daniel, 1996). Such events help to attract more visitors and promote the cultural heritage of the country. Due to the need for professionally organized concert halls, qualified teachers and dance schools, dance tourism also contributes to the development of

infrastructure and services. This contributes to the economic development of the region and leads to the creation of new jobs.

Attending dance events can also improve international connections and facilitate the exchange of cultural knowledge. As a result, dance tourism makes a significant contribution to the diversity of the country and attracts tourists. In conclusion, dance is a powerful art form that transcends cultural boundaries and serves as a universal language of human expression. This is an important aspect of human culture because it allows people to convey a variety of emotions, stories and ideas through body movements. Dance plays an important role in promoting intercultural dialogue and mutual understanding, as well as in shaping the identity of different nations. In addition, it has a profound effect on human mental health and is a form of entertainment, communication and self-expression. In general, the art of dance is an important and rich part of human existence, and its importance will continue to be felt in the coming years.

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